

Differential Pulse Polarographic Studies of the Tin Compounds used in Unani Medicine[†]

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Characterisation of tin compounds (*Kushta Qalai*) used in Unani medicine has been carried out in walpole buffer and Britton-Robinson buffer by differential pulse polarography. These results show that the tin compounds give characteristic differential pulse polarographic peaks in walpole buffer and exist in stannous form. The colorimetric studies were also performed for the estimation of solubility of tin in walpole buffer.

COMPOUNDS of different metal ions (*Kushta*) prepared under strictly specified alchemic conditions have been used in Unani and Ayurvedic systems of medicine. Inorganic compounds of metals are known as *Kushta* in Unani medicine¹. The function of these medicines is not understood due to lack of their characterisation. With the understanding of biological processes at the molecular level the key role of metal ions has been recognised². Keeping the recent developments in mind, the work on the characterisation of metal compounds used in Unani medicine has been started using electrochemical methods³ with special reference to differential pulse polarography (DPP). Here the results of the studies on tin compounds are reported using three different samples of *Kushta Qalai* in buffer solutions of pH 2.8 and 1.0.

Experimental

Kushta Qalai (tin compound) was obtained from three sources whose preparations are described below.

Sample 1: It was prepared at Hamdard Research Laboratories, Tughlaqabad, New Delhi. Tin foils (10 g; A.R.) were surrounded by fresh and crushed leaves (~1 kg) of 'bhang' (*Cannabis sativa*). It was winded up in a gunney bag and incinerated in the heat of 'upla dasti' (big size dung cake, 20 kg) away from the wind. After cooling, the whitish grey pieces of 'Kushta' were carefully handpicked, powdered, passed through 170 mesh and stored.

Sample 2: It was also prepared at Hamdard Laboratories. Alum (125 g) was roasted in an iron pan to whiteness and then powdered. Tin (250 g) was also roasted in an iron pan and at the time of melting powdered alum was sprinkled with vigorous stirring till all alum was consumed. Half-roasted tin was then removed and triturated in alvebarbed-ings (100 ml, juice of Gheekawar). Ten tablets

prepared from the mass was then subjected to Gile Hikmat process and incinerated in cow dung (10 kg) heat. On cooling white 'kushta' was obtained and stored.

Sample 3: It was a commercial sample (Makhzanul-Advia Majidia, Delhi).

Britton-Robinson buffer (pH 2.8) and walpole buffer (pH 1.0 and 2.78) were prepared by reported methods⁴.

An Elico pH-meter was used for pH-measurements. All the reagents were of A.R grade. DPP was recorded using a PARC polarographic analyser.

Differential pulse polarograms: To Britton-Robinson buffer (20 ml; pH 2.8), different samples of 'Kushta' were added separately to prepare saturated solutions. After keeping the mixtures for 24 h, the solutions were filtered and their differential pulse polarograms recorded. The procedure was repeated using walpole buffer solution (pH 1.0 and 2.78). Polarograms for SnCl_2 and SnCl_4 were also recorded. Purified nitrogen gas was used for removing the dissolved oxygen which interferes with the reduction of tin compounds.

Estimation of soluble tin: Walpole buffer (pH 1.0 and 2.78; 25 ml) was saturated by adding different samples (0.165 g) of tin compounds. After keeping the mixtures for 24 h, the solutions were filtered and the soluble tin (Sn^{II}) was estimated by the reported method⁵.

Results and Discussion

DPP polarograms (not shown) in walpole buffer reveal two peaks ($E_p \approx -0.60$ V and $E_p \approx -1.30$ V) for all the three samples while in Britton-Robinson buffer only one peak is observed at -1.30 V. The peak potentials (E_p) and peak currents (i_p) are given in Table I. In walpole buffer, the first peak is found to be associated with stannous form and the

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second one ($E_p \approx -1.30$ V) could not be definitely assigned and may be a catalytic reduction peak of hydrogen ion. In Britton-Robinson buffer, the reduction peak of stannous do not appear but the reduction peak ($E_p \approx -1.30$ V) is same as that of the second reduction peak of walpole buffer (Table 1).

TABLE 1—VALUES OF PEAK POTENTIALS (E_p) AND PEAK CURRENTS (i_p) OF DIFFERENT SAMPLES OF KUSHTA QALAI

Buffer solution	Peak	Sample 1		Sample 2		Sample 3	
		$-E_p$ V	i_p μA	$-E_p$ V	i_p μA	$-E_p$ V	i_p μA
Britton-Robinson buffer (pH=2.80)	I	—	—	—	—	—	—
	II	1.31	10.0	1.44	1300	1.34	29.5
Walpole buffer (pH=2.78)	I	0.63	8.0	0.58	20	0.62	34.5
	II	1.30	30.5	1.36	250	1.33	32.5
Walpole buffer (pH=1.0)	I	0.62	1.5	0.61	22	0.60	11.5
	II	1.39	7.3	1.33	1740	1.35	16.0

Colorimetric studies for the estimation of tin (stannous) shows that the tin compounds (Kushta qalai) are sparingly soluble in walpole buffer (Table 2). On the basis of these results, it may be concluded that the first peak ($E_p \approx -0.60$ V) is the reduction peak of stannous ion in walpole buffer. The ratio of soluble tin (stannous) varies in different samples and is dependent on the method of preparation of the Kushta. Therefore, just by looking at DPP polarographic data or concentration of stannous ion, one can tell about the source of Kushta and its nature. Now it remains to be decided by the

TABLE 2—CONCENTRATION OF SOLUBLE TIN (STANNOUS) IN DIFFERENT SAMPLES OF KUSHTA QALAI

Sample no.	pH=1.0 Concn. of Sn^{2+} $\times 10^{-4}$ mol dm^{-3}	pH=2.78 Concn. of Sn^{2+} $\times 10^{-4}$ mol dm^{-3}
	1	1.60
2	1.85	2.40
3	2.0	4.00

physicians whether stannous ion and its compound (Kushta) as a whole is the active species which is not at all understood at the moment and is beyond the scope of our studies.

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